

Genomes for Plant and Crop Science Research

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Southern Cross Plant Science

Faculty of Science and Engineering

Southern Cross University

Genomics for better informed (pre) breeding for crops of interest

Deep + broad understanding of genome organization

Phenotypic traits

Linkage

Genome

Functional & comparative genomics

CROP OMICS FOR GLOBAL NICHE CROPS

pre-breeding and breeding

Macadamia

Pre-breeding genetics/genome anchoring

Horticulture
Innovation
Australia

Tea Tree

Pre-breeding /breeding program + CRC-P

**Yellow sarson,
Mustard Oil**

Pre-breeding / breeding selection

Australian
Mustard Oils

**MULTINATIONAL BRASSICA
GENOME PROJECT (MBGP)**

Brassica rapa R-o-18 (yellow sarson)

SCU_BraROA_2.3

Organism name: [Brassica rapa subsp. trilocularis \(field mustard\)](#)

Infraspecific name: Ecotype: Yellow sarson

Isolate: R-o-18

BioSample: [SAMN16250067](#)

BioProject: [PRJNA649364](#)

Submitter: Brassica rapa R-o-18 genome sequencing consortium

Date: 2021/03/30

Prof. Graham J. King

GenBank accession: [GCA_017639395.1](#)

Molecule	Total Length	Scaffold Count	Ungapped Length	Scaffold N50	Spanned Gaps	Unspanned Gaps
All	346,506,900	295	345,222,260	32,457,817	855	0
Chromosome A10	22,576,415	1	22,526,320	22,576,415	57	0
Chromosome A01	34,445,504	1	33,995,968	34,445,504	89	0
Chromosome A02	36,095,996	1	36,038,788	36,095,996	73	0
Chromosome A03	32,457,817	1	32,448,697	32,457,817	20	0
Chromosome A04	23,305,641	1	23,284,797	23,305,641	36	0
Chromosome A05	32,871,474	1	32,825,490	32,871,474	76	0
Chromosome A06	30,241,088	1	30,224,719	30,241,088	32	0
Chromosome A07	27,715,701	1	27,692,758	27,715,701	19	0
Chromosome A08	25,318,967	1	25,286,307	25,318,967	31	0
Chromosome A09	60,281,870	1	60,145,694	60,281,870	162	0
unplaced	21,196,427	285	20,752,722	233,017	260	0

Community-driven improvement of R-o18 genome annotation ...

Curating and enriching identified seed storage protein gene models

Macadamia integrifolia HAES 741

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Chromosome-Scale Assembly and Annotation of the Macadamia Genome (*Macadamia integrifolia* HAES 741)

 Catherine J. Nock, Abdul Baten, Ramil Mauleon, Kirsty S. Langdon, Bruce Topp, Craig Hardner, Agnelo Furtado, Robert J. Henry and Graham J. King

G3: GENES, GENOMES, GENETICS October 1, 2020 vol. 10 no. 10 3497-3504;
<https://doi.org/10.1534/g3.120.401326>

Dr. Catherine Nock

ID: 34480

Organism Overview : [Organelle Annotation Report \[1\]](#)

Macadamia integrifolia

Macadamia integrifolia overview

Lineage: Eukaryota[7993]; Viridiplantae[842]; Streptophyta[758]; Embryophyta[752]; Tracheophyta[744]; Spermatophyta[733]; Magnoliopsida[717]; Proteales[3]; Proteaceae[2]; Macadamia[1]; Macadamia integrifolia[1]
Macadamia integrifolia genome reference project

Summary

Submitter:	Southern Cross University
Assembly level:	Chromosome
Assembly:	GCA_013358625.1 SCU_Mint_v3 scaffolds: 2,644 contigs: 23,449 N50: 60,651 L50: 3,405
BioProjects:	PRJNA748012
Whole Genome Shotgun (WGS):	INSDC: JAAEEG000000000.1
Statistics:	total length (Mb): 744.937 protein count: 46649 GC%: 39.2926
NCBI Annotation Release:	100

Community-driven improvement of macadamia genome annotation...

Improving gene models with data from new studies through the macadamia research community

Melaleuca alternifolia (tea tree)

Data Release

A high-quality draft genome for *Melaleuca alternifolia* (tea tree): a new platform for evolutionary genomics of myrtaceous terpene-rich species

Julia Voelker*, Mervyn Shepherd, Ramil Mauleon

DOI 10.46471/gigabyte.28

Views 300

Downloads 41

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Article Review History

Published online : 9
August 2021

PhD candidate Julia Voelker and
Dr. Mervyn Shepherd

SCU_Malt_1

Organism name: [Melaleuca alternifolia \(tea tree\)](#)

Isolate: SCU01

BioSample: [SAMN17927736](#)

BioProject: [PRJNA702189](#)

Submitter: Southern Cross University

Date: 2021/09/10

Assembly level: Scaffold

Genome representation: full

RefSeq category: representative genome

GenBank assembly accession: [GCA_019926035.1](#) (latest)

RefSeq assembly accession: n/a

RefSeq assembly and GenBank assembly identical: n/a

WGS Project: [JAGKPW01](#)

Assembly method: MaSuRCA v. 3.4.0

Expected final version: no

Genome coverage: 350.0x

Sequencing technology: PacBio Sequel; Illumina HiSeq

IDs: 10874731 [UID] 28792958 [GenBank]

Apollo usage example:

The manual annotation of the terpene synthase gene family in *Melaleuca alternifolia*

Julia Voelker

PhD candidate at the Faculty of Science and Engineering

Australian Myrtaceae

Melaleuca alternifolia (tea tree)

Eucalyptus grandis

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Australian Myrtaceae

Melaleuca alternifolia (tea tree)

→
Terpene
synthases
(TPS)

Terpenoids

573,750 575,000 576,250 577,500

User-created Annotations
scf7180000029212_mRNA_102-00001

fgenes
scf7180000029212_mRNA_102
protein supported,protein: gi 702517665 |ref|XP_010042263.1| PREDICTED: (-)-germacrene D synthase-like [Eucalyptus grandis]

genemark
45730_t 45731_t

exonerate

height reached Max height reached Max height reached Max height reached

Fgenes++
GenemarkET+

Exonerate TPS alignments

RNAseq alignments

Reference sequence

R K T N K R N A T M A L E S E A L Y L R K I S P P H M P G I I C S A F S Y V A C F L S W R R E E I K R G H F S F
E N E K K C N H G V G I R S L F E K I I P P Y A W M I I C S A F S Y V A C F L S W R R E E I K R G H F S F
AGAAAACGAATAAAAGAAATGCAACCATGGCGTTGGGAATCAGAAGCTTATTTGAGAAAATAATCCCCCATATGCTGGATGATAATTGCTGATCGGC
TCTTTTGCCTTATTTTCTTTTACGTTACCGCAACCTTAGTCTTTCGAATAAACTCTTTTATTAGGGGGGTATACGGACCTACTATTAACGACTAGCCG
L F R I F S I C G H R Q F F S I Q S F L G G M H R S S L K S I P T S H P R N G S S F I F L N S P V N R
L F V F L L F A V M A N S D S A K L F Y D G W I G P H Y N A S R R E A I H G T E K A P S S S S I Q L S M E
S F S Y F F H L W P T P I L L K N S F I I G G Y A Q I I I Q Q D A N L T A Q K R L Q L L H L S K F P C K R

User-created Annotations

fgenesch
genemark 21934_t

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University

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Plant Science

Thanks for your attention!

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BioCommons

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supercomputing centre